

The Role of Leadership in Managing Occupational Stress

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Abstract

This study examines the critical role that leadership style plays in managing occupational stress within organizational settings. Occupational stress continues to be a major challenge across industries, with direct implications for employee health, job satisfaction, and overall productivity. Through a systematic literature review using peer-reviewed sources from databases such as Scopus, JSTOR, and Google Scholar, this study explores how various leadership styles—transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire—either mitigate or intensify stress among employees. Transformational leadership, marked by empathy, vision, and support, is consistently associated with reduced stress and greater psychological resilience. In contrast, autocratic and inconsistent leadership approaches often correlate with burnout and emotional exhaustion. Despite the growing body of literature, a gap remains in understanding how leadership styles interact with contextual factors such as organizational culture, industry type, and employee demographics. This research addresses that gap and emphasizes the importance of emotional intelligence, open communication, and leader-member exchange in buffering occupational stress. The findings have practical implications for leadership development programs, suggesting that stress-reducing leadership can be cultivated through targeted training and policy reforms. This systematic review synthesizes findings from 95 studies to provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the leadership-stress nexus, offering evidence-based recommendations for both theory and practice.

Keywords: *Leadership, occupational stress, consequences, transformational leadership, authentic leadership, systematic review*

JEL Classification: M12, M54, I31, J28, O15

Introduction

Overview

Stress at work has become a widespread problem in modern businesses, impacting people and organizations in a variety of sectors. “Stress can be either useful or harmful to job performance” (Daneshvar, 2025; p. 13). Workplace stress is becoming an inevitable reality due to rising performance standards, short turnaround times, technological advancements, and unclear job

descriptions. According to Leka et al. (2003), prolonged exposure to this kind of stress might result in problems with one's physical and mental well-being, decreased productivity, and increased turnover rates. Although the causes and effects of occupational stress have been the subject of numerous studies, there has been a growing body of research on the impact of leadership style, an organizational aspect that may be changed. By influencing communication patterns, interpersonal relationships, and organizational culture, leadership can either reduce or increase employees' stress levels (Skakon et al., 2010). A mismatch between job demands and employees' ability to cope leads to the emergence of occupational stress (Haque, 2023; Kaur & Haque, 2024; Kaur & Haq, 2025). This paper's main goal is to critically analyze the ways in which different approaches to leadership impact on workers' occupational stress. It is also important to note that stress negatively affective the innovation (Haque, Yamoah, & Nweke, 2025). It specifically aims to determine which theories of leadership are best for workers' well-being and to examine the ways in which leadership can either reduce or increase stress.

Based on an analysis of previous research, this study examines the effects of four well-known leadership styles—transformational, transactional, servant, and laissez-faire—on work-related stress. The moderating effects of communication, workplace culture, and emotional intelligence are all considered in the analysis. The paper is limited to secondary data sources, particularly peer-reviewed research published in the last 15 years. This systematic review is conducted to address a gap in literature by synthesizing evidence on the efficacy of various leadership styles, including the increasingly relevant authentic and ethical leadership, in managing occupational stress across different sectors and cultures (Haque & Yamoah, 2021; Javed et al., 2018a).

Literature Review

“Leadership style is a leader's method to deliver guidance, executing plans, and motivating followers” (Imtiaz, 2025; p. 39). Different leadership styles have different effects on work-related stress. Because of their empathy, support, and vision, transformational and servant leadership are consistently associated with reduced stress (Haque & Yamoah, 2021). Authentic leadership has potential as well. Using PLS-SEM techniques, a cross-sectional study of software professionals in Pakistan and the UK (n = 220) discovered that genuine leadership greatly enhanced psychological capital and decreased organizational and personal stressors (Haque, Sher, & Urbański, 2020).

Another leadership approach that Haque & Yamoah (2021) promotes is ethical leadership, which works well in cross-cultural settings. Although Pakistani employees reported higher levels of stress but larger levels of innovation, ethical leadership in cargo logistics SMEs in Canada and Pakistan decreased occupational stress and increased innovative work behavior (Haque & Yamoah, 2021). These results emphasize the moderating effects of context and culture.

In a multi-sector study, Kaur et al. (2024) found that servant leadership had the greatest impact on team dynamics and project success, while autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles had a low correlation with favorable results (Kaur, Haque & Gkasis, 2024). Thus, it is important to note that different leadership styles affect differently, which means that there could enhance stress in a distinct manner.

Under transformational and inclusive leadership, it has also been repeatedly demonstrated that emotional intelligence and open communication reduce stress (Skakon et al., 2010; Javed et al., 2018b). Stress-leadership interactions are further moderated by employee demographics (gender, nationality) and organizational culture (supportive vs. hierarchical) (Faizan et al., 2018).

There is still a significant gap in literature: few research compares authentic, servant, and ethical

versions of positive leadership head-to-head in terms of stress reduction across various economies and industries. To answer it, this research synthesizes various leadership concepts and analyzes contextual variables. To provide a clear overview, Table 1 summarizes the key studies and their findings on the leadership-stress relationship.

Table 1: Summary of Key Findings from Literature Review

No.	Key Concept	Reference
1.	Authentic leadership enhances psychological capital and reduces occupational stress.	Haque, Sher, & Urbański (2020)
2.	Ethical leadership reduces stress and promotes innovation in cross-cultural contexts.	Haque & Yamoah (2021)
3.	Servant leadership positively impacts team dynamics, reducing collaborative stress.	Kaur, Haque, & Gkasis (2024)
4.	Inclusive leadership fosters voice behavior and reduces stress through psychological empowerment.	Younas, Wang, Javed, & Haque (2023)
5.	Transformational leadership is associated with lower stress and higher employee well-being.	Skakon et al. (2010)
6.	Laissez-faire leadership correlates with higher role ambiguity and stress.	Skakon et al. (2010)
7.	Occupational stress leads to burnout, absenteeism, and reduced productivity.	Kelloway & Barling (2010); Kaur (2023)
8.	Leadership influences stress outcomes differently across sectors (e.g., IT, healthcare).	Haque, Aston, & Kozlovski (2016)
9.	Psychological empowerment mediates the relationship between leadership and stress.	Javed et al. (2018a) Javed et al. (2018b)
10.	Gender and cultural dynamics moderate the stress-leadership relationship.	Faizan & Haque (2019); Haque & Yamoah (2021)

Source: *author's illustration based on secondary studies*

Research Methodology

A systematic literature review design is used in this study. Peer-reviewed journal publications, empirical studies, and edited volumes including editing volumes by Haque Handbooks on Occupational Stress, 2022–2023 (Haque, 2022; Haque, 2023)—are among the sources. JSTOR, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar are among the databases that were searched. “Leadership style,” “occupational stress,” “genuine leadership,” “ethical leadership,” “transformational leadership,” and “servant leadership” were among the search terms. This systematic review adheres to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency and rigor. The methodology is structured into four phases: (1) Search Strategy, (2) Study Selection and Eligibility Criteria, (3) Data Extraction and Synthesis, and (4) Quality Assessment. Table 2 contains the criteria applied for inclusion-and-exclusion for commencing research.

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Publications within the last 15 years (2010–2025)	Anecdotal or non-peer-reviewed sources Leadership unrelated to employee stress

Empirical or review-based studies that analyze leadership style effects stress Studies in diverse geographic and industry contexts (e.g. IT, logistics SMEs)	management. Non-English publications. Studies with insufficient methodological rigor.
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Source: *author's illustration*

After applying these criteria, 95 studies were selected for inclusion in the review. The search was further refined using Boolean operators (AND, OR) function, and filters were applied to include only peer-reviewed articles published in English between 2010 and 2024. The inclusion of recent and relevant studies was ensured while it was ensured that scope remains manageable within this time frame.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data extraction was conducted using a standardized form that included the following fields:

- Study details: Author(s), year, journal, title
- Methodology: Research design, country, sample size, sector
- Key variables: Antecedents, outcomes, and consequences of occupational stress and leadership
- Major findings: Key insights and sector-specific differences

Thematic analysis was used to synthesize the extracted data and identify recurring themes and patterns. Three main themes were identified from the findings: (1) leadership, (2) causes and outcomes of occupational stress, and (3) the interplay between leadership and occupational stress. The findings were synthesized under the following themes: (1) The Impact of Leadership Styles on Occupational Stress, (2) Sector-Specific Analysis, and (3) Mediating Mechanisms.

Bibliometric Analysis

To provide a comprehensive overview of the included studies, a bibliometric analysis was conducted. Table 2 summarizes the key characteristics of the studies, including publication trends, geographical distribution, and sector-specific focus.

Table 2: Bibliometric Analysis of Included Studies

Category	Details	Number of Studies	Percentage
Publication Year	2010–2015	15	15.8%
	2016–2020	35	36.8%
	2021–2025	45	47.4%
Geographical Region	North America	30	31.6%
	Europe	25	26.3%
	Asia	28	29.5%
	Other	12	12.6%
Sector Focus	Healthcare	25	26.3%
	IT & Technology	20	21.1%
	Education	18	18.9%
	Manufacturing/Logistics	15	15.8%
	Other (Finance, Public Sector)	17	17.9%
Research Design	Quantitative	70	73.7%
	Qualitative	15	15.8%

	Mixed Methods	10	10.5%
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Source: *author's illustration based on secondary studies*

Qualitative Assessment

The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) was used to evaluate the methodological quality of the included studies. Studies were assessed based on their research design, sampling strategy, and data analysis. Low-scoring studies were excluded to ensure the validity and reliability of the synthesized findings.

Findings and Discussions

Through a synthesis of the literature and a comparative analysis, this part aims to assess the role of leadership style in controlling occupational stress. The results demonstrate the negative effects of mismanaged stress as well as the moderating function of leadership in various organizational settings. The evidence is presented methodically in three tables and one figure, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the data in addition to theoretical ideas.

Occupational Stress Outcomes

According to the literature, workplace stress has a significant impact on both businesses and individual workers. Chronic stress causes employee burnout, absenteeism, decreased productivity, and higher intentions to leave (Kelloway & Barling, 2010; Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Additionally, it causes mental and physical health issues such as depression, anxiety, and exhaustion (WHO, 2010). The main effects of occupational stress found in several studies are compiled in Table 4.

Table 4: Occupational Stress Outcomes

Outcome	Impact Level	Reference
Reduced Productivity	High	Leka et al. (2003)
Increased Absenteeism	Moderate to High	Kelloway & Barling (2010)
Employee Burnout	High	Maslach & Leiter (2016)
Decreased Job Satisfaction	High	Skakon et al. (2010)
Turnover Intentions	Moderate	Haque et al. (2015)
Physical Health Problems	Moderate to High	WHO (2010)
Mental Health Issues	High	Haque & Yamoah (2021)

Source: *Findings based on the critical review of the literature at hand*

Significantly detrimental organizational results are correlated with high levels of occupational stress, as Table 4 illustrates. This is in line with Haque and Yamoah (2021), who underline that unresolved stress adds to systemic inefficiencies in businesses in addition to jeopardizing employee well-being. By offering psychological safety, transparent communication, and

supporting practices, transformational and authentic leadership have been found to operate as moderating variables that mitigate these adverse effects (Skakon et al., 2010). The high prevalence of these outcomes underscores the critical need for effective organizational interventions, with leadership being a primary lever for change.

Leadership Styles Across Industries

The influence of leadership style on occupational stress varies by industry and is influenced by employee expectations, corporate culture, and work demands. The most successful leadership styles found in various industries are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Leadership Styles Across Industries

Industry	Most Effective Leadership Style(s)	Stress Impact	Reference Example
Healthcare	Transformational / Servant	Lower stress, higher resilience	Skakon et al. (2010)
Education	Authentic / Ethical	Reduced teacher burnout	Haque et al. (2020)
Corporate/Business	Transformational / Transactional	Balanced productivity and stress control	Haque et al. (2015)
Public Sector	Authentic / Transformational	Improved trust and reduced political stress	Kelloway & Barling (2010)
IT & Technology	Authentic / Ethical	Reduced stress: fosters trust and manages innovation pressure	Javed et al. (2018a); Haque et al. (2016)

Source: *Sectoral analysis based on secondary data*

By empowering employees and encouraging teamwork, servant and transformational leadership styles in the healthcare industry reduce stress levels brought on by lengthy workdays and emotional tiredness (Skakon et al., 2010). By fostering trust, openness, and moral decision-making, authentic leadership in education has been demonstrated to lower teacher burnout (Haque et al., 2020). A combination of transformational and transactional leadership, on the other hand, has shown promise in business settings. While transformational leaders encourage sustained motivation, transactional strategies offer structure and clarity, lowering stress brought on by ambiguity (Faizan et al., 2018). Together, transformative and authentic leadership in the public sector reduces the stress brought on by bureaucratic obstacles and political demands while enhancing management trust (Kelloway & Barling, 2010). The inclusion of the IT sector highlights the relevance of authentic and ethical leadership in managing stress within high-pressure, innovative environments (Javed et al., 2018b).

Stress Symptoms and Prevalence

Evaluating how leadership lessens the effects of stress requires an understanding of its expressions. Based on earlier research, Table 6 shows the frequency of behavioral, emotional, and physical stress symptoms.

Table 6: Stress Symptoms Prevalence

Symptom Category	Examples	Prevalence (%)	Reference Example
Physical	Headaches, fatigue, sleep disturbance	65	WHO (2010)
Emotional	Anxiety, depression, irritability	55	Maslach & Leiter (2016)
Behavioral	Absenteeism, reduced collaboration, errors	45	Leka et al. (2003)

Source: *Findings based on secondary data analysis*

The data demonstrates that physical symptoms of stress are most prevalent (65%), followed by emotional (55%) and behavioral (45%) symptoms. These findings are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: *Prevalence of Occupational Stress Symptoms*

The high prevalence of physical and emotional symptoms underscores the urgency of proactive stress management strategies. Leadership plays a vital role in early identification and mitigation. For example, transformational leaders can foster resilience by promoting optimism and organizational commitment, reducing emotional exhaustion (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Likewise, authentic leaders foster psychological safety, encouraging employees to report stress symptoms without fear of stigma (Haque et al., 2019).

The results confirm that management of occupational stress in various organizational contexts is greatly influenced by leadership style. While transactional leadership may work well when paired with more sympathetic methods, research consistently indicates that transformational and authentic leadership offer the most stress-reduction benefits.

Contradictions are also revealed by literature, though. For example, servant leadership may not be as beneficial in corporate settings because performance-driven cultures require more transactional control, even though it is quite effective in the healthcare industry (Faizan et al., 2018). The dangers of leader disengagement are further highlighted by the persistent correlation between laissez-faire leadership and higher levels of stress and poorer levels of satisfaction (Skakon et al., 2010).

These findings align with Haque et al. (2019) emphasis on contextual leadership, which advocates situational flexibility rather than rigid adherence to a single style while stress impact the individuals differently (Haque & Aston, 2016). Furthermore, the WHO (2010) warned that occupational stress is a developing worldwide health concern that requires proactive leadership solutions, and the incidence of stress symptoms (Figure 1) supports this warning. Overall, the synthesis shows that leadership has a critical role in determining occupational well-being rather than only acting as a moderate factor. Leaders may strike a balance between reducing workplace stress and increasing staff performance by fusing transformational inspiration, authentic transparency, and transactional clarity. The mediating roles of psychological empowerment (Javed et al., 2018b) and high-quality leader-member exchange (Haque & Yamoah, 2021) are identified as critical mechanisms through which positive leadership buffers stress.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This review underscores that authentic, ethical, and servant leadership styles are most effective at mitigating occupational stress across varied cultural and organizational contexts. Transformational leadership remains relevant but may be complemented by authenticity and service orientation for greater impact. Emotional intelligence and inclusive communication serve as key mediators. The sectoral analysis confirms that there is no one-size-fits-all approach, and leadership development must be context-sensitive.

Research Limitations

Despite the robust synthesis of secondary literature, several limitations constrain this study. First,

the reviewed literature is largely concentrated in healthcare and education, with limited exploration of rapidly evolving sectors such as technology startups, creative industries, and the gig economy. Second, reliance on cross-sectional survey methods and self-reported data introduces potential bias, as employees may underreport or overreport stress levels based on perception rather than measurable outcomes. Third, much of the existing research originates in Western contexts, which may not fully capture cultural variations in leadership practices and occupational stress responses. Finally, the theoretical lens in many studies has centered primarily on transformational leadership, leaving newer approaches such as digital, distributed, or hybrid leadership underexplored.

Future Directions

- Empirical, multi-method studies comparing multiple leadership styles within a single organizational context.
- Industry-specific research (e.g. healthcare, education, manufacturing) to evaluate generalizability.
- Longitudinal designs to assess long-term impact of leadership training on stress reduction.
- Investigation into the role of leadership in managing stress within remote and hybrid work models.
- Cross-cultural studies to validate the universality or cultural specificity of stress-reducing leadership behaviors.

Practical Recommendations

- Organizations should invest in leadership development programs that build authenticity, ethical decision-making, and servant-oriented behaviors.
- HR policies should promote emotional intelligence training and open communication channels.
- Cultural adaptation of leadership development is critical for multinational or diverse organizations.
- Implement 360-degree feedback systems to identify and remediate negative leadership behaviors that contribute to stress.
- Develop sector-specific leadership frameworks; for example, emphasizing servant leadership in healthcare and authentic leadership in knowledge-intensive industries like IT.

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